

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGE AS THE SECOND LANGUAGE

Nasimova Sohiba Yaxyayevna
Samarkand State Medical University
Department of Languages
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10128980>

Abstract. This article represents research work on psychological aspects of learning foreign language as the second language. Over several decades, modern society has undergone fundamental social transformations, which has led to the need for professional psychologists. The need for specialists who are able to solve practical problems in providing psychological support and solving important acute social problems has only been increasing over recent years. For that reason, the problem of studying the training of highly qualified specialists working in the human-human interaction system becomes particularly important. In this case, an important issue in this area that deserves special attention is the study of the mental development of students and the factors that influence them in the learning process.

Key words: mental, educational institution, linguistics, teacher-student, foreign language,

Introduction. One of the 3 features of the “teacher-student” relationship is an individual approach and status-role differences in behavior. First of all, this depends on the general psychological climate in the educational institution. For a student, an adequate assessment of the relationship with the teacher is formed in conditions of creative cooperation. Such relationships increase interest both in the personality of the teacher and in the subject itself, which makes it possible to transform the student’s thinking, the level of his development of cognitive activity, interests and attitude towards educational activities.

Sitting in the classroom and encountering this subject for the first time, do you feel afraid of the person giving the lecture questions arise: does the teacher know the subject? Will the lecture be interesting? What new facts will he (the student) learn? How is the test/exam conducted? The communicative characteristics of the teacher also characterize his personal qualities. However, psychological adaptation consists not only of didactic or communicative adaptation, it is the individual’s entry into the system of intra-group relations, adaptation to these relations, the development of such thinking and behavior that reflect the system of values and norms of this group, the acquisition, consolidation and development of new skills and abilities interpersonal cognition for effective communication in this group (Rozhdestvenskaya N.A.). Age, as well as learning conditions, play an important role in the learning process. To take into account the patterns and mechanisms of a person’s mental development and his personal formation in life, developmental psychology helps us. To study the mechanisms and patterns of a person’s mastery of sociocultural experience in the educational process (including the acquisition of foreign languages), educational psychology helps us.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language at the threshold level is the formation of communicative competence, where several components are distinguished: linguistic

competence, sociolinguistic, sociocultural competence, strategic, discursive and social competence. Since ancient times, language and speech have aroused comprehensive interest in study, being insufficiently studied problems due to their complexity and interconnectedness with the mental side of human life. The forerunner of psycholinguistics A.A. Leontiev names the German philosopher and linguist Wilhelm von Humboldt, because it was he who owned "the idea of speech activity and the understanding of language as a connecting link between society and man" (A.A. Leontiev). The subject of psycholinguistics is the relationship of personality with the structure and functions of speech activity, as well as language as the main element that forms the image of the human world.

One of the psychological and methodological concepts of teaching foreign languages belongs to B.V. Belyaev. The key idea behind the concept is to provide an instrumental component of the process of teaching foreign languages. Assistance in improving the methodology is for B.V. Belyaev is fundamental in the psychological process of teaching foreign languages. In his opinion, psychology lies precisely at the basis of the methodology and represents a fundamentally correct relationship between methodology and psychology. In adolescence, the process of development of cognition is actively underway. Teenagers have already developed logical thinking and the ability to introspect.

They are able to think on various topics, draw general conclusions based on particular premises and, conversely, reason from the general to the specific. Leontyev A.A. showed that with increasing age there is a gradual improvement in direct memorization, and faster than indirect memory. In comparison with a child, an adult student is considered as an active subject of pedagogical interaction who can independently organize his activities. Modern foreign language teaching is based on a student-oriented approach to learning, which assumes that all methodological decisions of the teacher "should be refracted through the prism the personality of the student - his needs, motives, abilities, activity, intelligence and other individual psychological characteristics". In this case, the student's personality is considered as a subject of pedagogical activity, who independently determines the nature of this activity and communication. Of particular importance today is the differentiation and individualization of the learning process. The study of cognitive styles directly expresses the individual uniqueness of the nature of the connection between all human properties (V.S. Merlin).

The creators of one of the most famous multicomponent systems of individuality, J. Royce and A. Powell, define individuality as a structure of psychological characteristics, which is determined by six interacting systems - sensory, motor, cognitive, affective, as well as a system of styles and a system of values.

The cognitive system is concerned with analyzing and processing information. The affective system activates processed information. Based on this, the cognitive and affective systems are the main elements responsible for processing information. The style system is closely related to the value system, since it depends on the generalization and transformation of information received from the cognitive and affective systems. In addition to all this, the style system is responsible for choosing ways to process information. The value system also summarizes information, but not to choose a method of action, but in order to highlight goals and determine opportunities and ways to achieve them. It is important to note that style and value systems, like the cognitive and affective systems, are associated with information processing, but the level of generalization provided by these systems is higher. It turns out

that they integrate information at the level of a holistic individuality. Individuality is based on differences in the volitional, intellectual, motivational spheres, in the properties of the nervous system, temperament, etc.

Individual style reflects the characteristics of the system of operations to which a person is predisposed due to his individual properties and is a system of ways of verbal transformation of information, formed on the basis of 9 motives and goals of activity through the mediation of cognitive styles by words, which are interpreted as individual operational systems of ways of processing information in the pre-verbal level. Cognitive styles determine the individual psychological characteristics of cognitive processes, the tendency to use characteristic ways of interacting with information. Based on all that has been said, we can conclude that cognitive style refers to the procedural characteristics of cognitive activity. Style parameters are compared with many different psychological characteristics of the individual (sensorimotor characteristics and psychophysiological characteristics, including temperament).

Cognitive style is associated with all levels of individual properties, influences the individual style of activity and itself depends on it. Located between the mental and personal levels of individuality, cognitive styles are considered as a way for an individual to master the picture of the world, including language. In foreign and domestic literature on psychology, there are about one and a half dozen individual techniques for handling information (cognitive style parameters). According to psychologists, individual values of people for each of these cognitive styles are located between the poles, forming a uniform distribution. People who are at the extreme end of any cognitive style are less adaptive than those in the middle of the range. The most adaptive are those with a mobile cognitive style, who can consciously change the settings of their cognitive apparatus based on the conditions of the situation. Personal and intellectual maturity help students combine the ability to act differently depending on the requirements of the situation, while maintaining some attraction to one of the poles. Mobility is considered by psychologists to be evidence of the high maturity of a person's cognitive structures.

Thus, we can conclude that individualization at the basis of cognitive styles largely determines the development of the style of individual activity, which develops as an integral effect of the interaction of the individual with the subject and social environment and can change with changes in activity conditions, is developed in the process of development, training and education.

As noted by M.A. Cold, learning to communicate in a foreign language taking into account cognitive styles implies the creation of conditions both for updating the existing system of stylistic characteristics of intellectual behavior, and for expanding the composition of stylistic behavior by mastering different styles at different levels of stylistic behavior, as well as for the interaction of different cognitive styles when studying any educational topic, mastering concepts and solving problems. Thus, in the psycholinguistic approach, language is considered not as a subject to be studied, but as a skill that a person needs to master and be able to use correctly. From this position, the teacher's task is to develop this skill. Therefore, in such a process it is necessary to use not only linguistic, but also psycholinguistic techniques that are based on the true motives of human behavior. These techniques are based on the assertion that language is a system, a means of communication, and not a set of grammatical rules. The linguistic-psychological approach considers memorizing individual words with

their translation as an ineffective technique, since human thinking is associative and it is not the word that remains in memory, but the process. It is recommended to memorize not individual words, but entire texts. At the initial stage of training, these may be small dialogues. Then their complexity and volume increases. As teachers note, in this case the main point is memorization, and not retelling, since when retelling, the student involuntarily remembers the content of the text in his native language and mentally translates it, which slows down speech reproduction. In the case of memorization, he reproduces ready-made clichés and subsequently uses them in the right situation, which is also an element of immersion.

Conclusion: Having analyzed a number of works by domestic psychologists, it can be noted that knowledge of pedagogical and developmental psychology, as well as the formation of motivation in the process of teaching foreign languages, helps to determine the patterns of mastering sociocultural experience and the features of the organization of the educational process that influences the student's cognitive activity. Taking into account cognitive styles in the learning process is directly related to the assimilation of information, the formation of knowledge, skills, and abilities, and contributes to further interpersonal communication.

References:

1. YOROVA, S., & NASIMOVA, S. THE WAYS OF TEACHING LANGUAGES AT MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS. PUBLISHING BOARD: Prof. Dzmitry Lazouski (chairperson); Dr. Dzmitry Hlukhau (vice-chairperson); Mr. Siarhei Piashkun (vice-chairperson); Dr. Maryia Putrava, 7.
2. Karimovna, Y. S. (2022). The linguistic environment in the field of medical communications. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(2), 143-147.
3. Shodikulova, A. (2023). COHESIONS FORMED BY MEANS OF HYPONYMS. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 3(9), 40-43.
4. Шодикулова, А. З. *Asian journal of multidimensional research. India (AJMRI) Vol, 9, 151-152.*
5. Aitmuratova, P., Yorova, S., & Esanova, M. (2023). THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN OUR LIFE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(4), 161-164.
6. Shamsiyev, K., Olimzoda, P., Saidova, K., & Ibragimova, D. (2023, February). APPROACHES TO TEACHING ACADEMIC WRITING. In *Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 31-34).*
7. Saidova, K., Ibragimova, D., Olimzoda, P., & Shamsiyev, K. (2023). INFLUENCE OF USING GAMES ON ENGLISH LESSONS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(4), 54-58.
8. Yaxyaevna, N. S. (2023). ANALYZING DIALECTS AND WRITTEN DOCUMENTS IN MIDDLE ENGLISH PERIOD. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 458-463.
9. Parvina, O. (2023). Theoretical and Methodological Foundations for the Formation of Communicative Competence of Medical Students. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education*, 1(3), 1-3.
10. Saidova, K., Ibragimova, D., Olimzoda, P., & Shamsiyev, K. (2023). INFLUENCE OF USING GAMES ON ENGLISH LESSONS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(4), 54-58.
11. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского*

государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции–знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных (р. 455).

12. Dilbar, I., & Kamola, S. (2022). TEACHING ENGLISH METHODS. Thematics Journal of Education, 7(5).

13. Anvarovna, T. N., & Toshmuratovna, T. C. (2021). The Vital Issues of Teaching Foreign Languages. Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 3, 45-47.

14. Zikiryaevna, S. A. (2023). JAHON ADABIYOTI NAMOYONDASI JEYMS JOYS HIKOYALARI. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 1(10), 123-125.

15. Zikiryaevna, S. A. (2022). Cognitive Interpretation Of The Phenomenon Of Metonymy. Eurasian Medical Research Periodical, 5, 102-104.

